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3 **A coupled plasticity and damage constitutive model considering residual shear**
4 **strength for shales**

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10 **Abstract:**

11 Shales are the most common materials on the Earth's surface that are frequently encountered in
12 various energy, environmental and engineering applications. Numerically predicting the
13 mechanical behavior of shales is of great importance in the geomechanics community. A coupled
14 plasticity-damage constitutive model is developed in this study to describe the mechanical
15 behavior of shales that spans the pre-peak, peak and post-peak regions. A concept of a damaged
16 part of geomaterials, which possesses residual shear strength, is introduced in the proposed model.
17 A thermodynamic conjugate force is presented by accounting for the residual shear strength of the
18 damaged part. Procedures to determine the model input parameters and an algorithm to implement
19 the constitutive model in a numerical code are presented. Validation against experimentally
20 observed stress-strain curves of shales shows that the proposed model can predict the mechanical
21 behavior of shales under various stress paths and confining stresses from the pre- to post-failure
22 regimes.

23 **Keywords:** coupled plasticity and damage; constitutive model; shale; residual strength; triaxial
24 tests

25 **Introduction**

26 Shales are the most ubiquitous materials on the Earth's surface and are frequently encountered in
27 various energy, environmental and engineering applications (Busch et al. 2008; Dayal 2017; Xue
28 et al. 2009; Ferrari and Laloui 2013). For instance, shales act as natural cap rocks for: 1)
29 underground sequestration of CO₂, and 2) for conventional and unconventional oil and gas

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30 reservoirs. They are also strong candidates as geologic barriers for nuclear waste disposal.
31 Improved understanding and prediction of the constitutive behavior of shales are important
32 challenges in the geomechanics community.

33 Numerous studies have shown that shales exhibit quasi-brittle behavior (Horsrud et al. 1998).
34 Under compressive stresses, quasi-brittle geomaterials show complex mechanical behavior
35 including elastic stiffness degradation, strain hardening/softening, irreversible strains, confining
36 pressure dependency, and anisotropy in strength, etc. The stress-strain curves of shales initially
37 show linear elastic deformation. This is followed by elastic stiffness degradation due to the
38 accumulation of small plastic strains induced by the occurrences of micro-crack initiation, crack
39 propagation and coalescence. After reaching the peak stress, shales enter the strain softening stage
40 in which the accumulated cracks reach a certain level and the irreversible strains increase
41 significantly. Finally, shales enter a residual shear stress level in which the carrying capacity of
42 shales remains almost constant.

43 To properly model the mechanical behavior of quasi-brittle materials, inelastic models as well as
44 the coupled damage and plasticity models have been developed. These two types of models can
45 simulate the softening behavior of geomaterials by introducing the damage theory to describe the
46 damage induced elastic degradation. The inelastic models (Maimi et al., 2007; Matallah and
47 Borderie, 2009; Monnamitheen and Dinkler, 2017) in which plasticity is not coupled, however,
48 cannot predict the permanent irreversible strains generated during the excessive loading. Coupled
49 damage and plasticity models (Shao et al., 1998; Chiarelli et al., 2003; Salari et al., 2004, Grassl
50 and Jirásek, 2006, Parisio et al., 2015, and Zhang et al., 2016), on the other hand, employ the
51 plastic mechanism to reflect the accumulated irreversible strain.

52 The failure process of shales can be reasonably associated with two physical phenomena at the
53 microscopic scale: the growth of microcracks and frictional sliding along closed cracks (Walsh,
54 1980). The crack growth results in material damage which can be described by the damage
55 mechanism. The frictional sliding leads to macroscopic irreversible strains which can be described
56 by plasticity theory. These two processes are inherently coupled in the failure and post-failure
57 processes in shales. The accumulation of frictional sliding leads to more microcracks which in turn
58 enhances the frictional sliding. In this sense, the mechanical behavior of shales can be better
59 described using a damage mechanism that is coupled to plasticity theory. Coupled damage-
60 plasticity models are typically derived from energy and dissipation potentials using a full
61 thermodynamic approach (Salari et al., 2004; Shao et al. 2006). The couplings are implicitly
62 introduced in the plastic yield function and damage criterion function. The plastic strain
63 multiplier and damage variable can be determined simultaneously according to thermodynamic
64 consistency.

65 Microcracks are developed and formed in geomaterials due to increasing external loads. Damaged
66 material in the inelastic models and in the coupled plasticity and damage models is treated as voids
67 which could not provide any resistances to the external loads. This is equivalent to say that the
68 damaged part of the material possesses no residual strength. To model the residual strength, one

69 could introduce a parameter β_d with $0 \leq \beta_d \leq 1$ to scale down the damage $\beta_d \times D$ (Parisio et al.
 70 2015; Zhang et al. 2016), which implies that $100 \times (1 - \beta_d \times D)\%$ of the ‘damaged material’ is
 71 still intact. An alternative approach in which the damaged part still possesses residual strength is
 72 introduced by Gao et al. (2017) and Zhao et al. (2017) in their inelastic models with the objective
 73 of simulating the residual strength. However, existing coupled plasticity-damage models do not
 74 consider this concept and treat the damaged part as voids which do not possess residual strength.

75 In this paper, a coupled plasticity-damage model is formulated in the framework of continuum
 76 thermodynamics to simulate mechanical behavior of shales. The concept of the residual strength,
 77 embodied in the work of Gao et al. (2017) and Zhao et al. (2017), is introduced in the proposed
 78 constitutive model to better account for the residual shear strength of shales. Triaxial tests on a
 79 North Sea shale were conducted under various confining stresses. The experimentally observed
 80 stress-strain curves were used to validate the proposed model.

81 Residual strength and thermodynamics framework

82 The concept of the damaged part of geomaterials that still possesses residual strength is introduced
 83 herein. Fig. 1 schematically shows the diagram of the damage evolution of geomaterials. The total
 84 force applied on the geomaterial can be decomposed into the force carried by the intact part and
 85 the force by the damaged part:

$$86 \quad \sigma A = \tilde{\sigma}^{in} A_{in} + \sigma^d A_d \quad (1)$$

$$87 \quad \text{and } A = A_{in} + A_d \quad (2)$$

88 where σ is the nominal stress; $\tilde{\sigma}^{in} = \mathbf{C}_0 : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e$ is the ‘damage effective stress’ acting on the
 89 undamaged area of the material; σ^d is the residual stress acting on the completely damaged portion
 90 of the material; A is the total loading surface of the material subjected to external load σA ; A_{in} and
 91 A_d are, respectively, the areas of the intact portion and the damaged portion of the material.

92

93

Fig. 1 Schematic diagram of the damage evolution process.

94

The scalar isotropic damage variable D is then defined as:

$$95 \quad D = \frac{A_d}{A} \quad (3)$$

96 where D is in the range of $0 \leq D \leq 1$.

97 Dividing the two sides of Eq. (1) by A and substituting $\tilde{\sigma}^{in} = \mathbf{C}_0 : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e$ and Eqs. (2) and (3) into Eq.
98 (1) leads to:

$$99 \quad \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{C}_d : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e + \boldsymbol{\sigma}^d D \quad (4)$$

$$100 \quad \text{and } \mathbf{C}_d = (1 - D)\mathbf{C}_0 \quad (5)$$

101 $\boldsymbol{\sigma}^d D$ defines the residual strength carried by the damaged part of the material. $\boldsymbol{\sigma}^d$ is defined as R
102 times of the peak strength $\boldsymbol{\sigma}^p$:

$$103 \quad \boldsymbol{\sigma}^d = R \times \boldsymbol{\sigma}^p \quad (6)$$

104 where R is the limit of the damage variable which is defined as the ratio of the residual strength to
105 the peak strength.

106 The rate form of Eq. (4) is expressed as:

$$107 \quad \dot{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} = -\dot{D}\mathbf{C}_0 : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e + \mathbf{C}_d : \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^e + \boldsymbol{\sigma}^d \dot{D} \quad (7)$$

108 Assuming an isothermal process, the Helmholtz free energy is considered to be a function of three
109 state variables: elastic strain $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e$, scalar damage variable D and internal variable for plastic
110 hardening γ_p :

$$111 \quad \psi(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e, \gamma_p, D) \quad (8)$$

112 The Helmholtz free energy can be decomposed into two parts: an elastic part $\psi^e(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e, D)$ and a
113 plastic part $\psi^p(\gamma_p, D)$:

$$114 \quad \psi(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e, \gamma_p, D) = \psi^e(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e, D) + \psi^p(\gamma_p, D) \quad (9)$$

115 The following Clausius-Duhem inequality must hold in order to satisfy the second principle of
116 thermodynamics:

$$117 \quad \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} - \dot{\psi} \geq 0 \quad (10)$$

118 The stress state $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ can be derived from the derivation of the thermodynamic potential:

$$119 \quad \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e} \quad (11)$$

120 Considering the definition of the stress state in Eq. (4), the elastic part of the Helmholtz free energy
121 $\psi^e(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e, D)$ can be defined as following:

$$122 \quad \psi^e(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e, D) = \frac{1}{2}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} - \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p) : \mathbf{C}_d : (\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} - \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p) + (1 - D)\boldsymbol{\sigma}^d : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e \quad (12)$$

123 The thermodynamic conjugate force associated with the damage variable can be derived with
124 reference to elastic and plasticity-damage as:

$$125 \quad Y_d = -\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial D} = -\frac{1}{2}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} - \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p) : \mathbf{C}'_d : (\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} - \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p) + \boldsymbol{\sigma}^d : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e - \frac{\partial \psi^p(\gamma_p, D)}{\partial D} \quad (13)$$

126 where \mathbf{C}'_d is a fourth order tensor which is the derivative of elastic tensor with respect to damage
127 variable:

$$128 \quad \mathbf{C}'_d = \frac{\partial \mathbf{C}_d}{\partial D} \quad (14)$$

129 The Clausius-Duhem inequality now becomes:

$$130 \quad \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} + Y_d \dot{D} \geq 0 \quad (15)$$

131

132 **Plasticity model and damage model**

133 The formulation of the coupled plasticity-damage model requires appropriate plasticity criterion
134 and damage criterion. To realistically describe the stress-dependent behavior of geomaterials, a
135 nonlinear quadratic formulation is used as the plastic yield criterion:

$$136 \quad f^p(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, \gamma_p, D) = q^2 - f^\theta(\theta)h(1 - D)(p - q_0) \quad (16a)$$

137 where p denotes the mean effective stress; q is the deviatoric stress; h is material parameter; D is
138 the scalar-valued damage parameter; q_0 is a material parameter.

139 Many rocks including shales have naturally inherent anisotropic structure, such as bedding planes
140 and rock joints, which induce direction-dependent response and anisotropy in mechanical behavior
141 of rocks. One simple and effective way to model the anisotropic effects is to directly add a
142 parameter in the failure envelope (Saroglou and Tsiambaos, 2008; Bagheripour et al., 2011; Ismael
143 et al. 2014). In this study, an “anisotropic function” $f(\theta)$ is incorporated in the failure envelope
144 Eq. (16a) with the objective to consider the anisotropic characteristics of shales. The function $f(\theta)$,
145 which represents the effect of strength anisotropy, depends on the angle between the σ_1 loading
146 direction and the bedding planes. The angle θ is measured from the major principle stress σ_1 to
147 the bedding plane as illustrated in Fig. 2.

148 The anisotropic function $f(\theta)$ is proposed to have the following form:

$$149 \quad f(\theta) = \frac{kc}{(1+k)+(1-k)\cos(3\theta+d)} \quad (16b_1)$$

$$150 \quad f(\theta) = \begin{cases} \frac{k_1c_1}{(1+k_1)+(1-k_1)\cos(3\theta+d_1)} & \theta \leq \theta_{min} \\ \frac{k_2c_2}{(1+k_2)+(1-k_2)\cos(3\theta+d_2)} & \theta \geq \theta_{min} \end{cases} \quad (16b_2)$$

151 where k , d , and c are anisotropy related parameters; $k = k_1$, $d = d_1$, $c = c_1$, for $\theta \leq \theta_{min}$;
 152 $k = k_2$, $d = d_2$, $c = c_2$, for $\theta \geq \theta_{min}$. θ_{min} is the angle which gives the lowest shear strength.
 153 More discussions will be given on the function $f(\theta)$ in the following.

154
 155 Fig. 2 The angle θ between the major principle stress σ_1 and the bedding plane.

156
 157 The material parameter h is expressed as a function of the equivalent deviatoric plastic strain γ_p
 158 (Shao et al. 1998):

$$159 \quad h = h_m - (h_m - h_0)e^{-b\gamma_p} \quad (17)$$

160 where h_0 and h_m are the initial and final yield values of the material parameter h , respectively. h_0
 161 determines the initial plastic yield threshold while h_m control the final surface. The parameters b
 162 are associated with the plastic hardening rate.

163 The equivalent deviatoric plastic strain γ_p is defined as:

$$164 \quad \gamma_p = \int \sqrt{\frac{2}{3} d\mathbf{e}^p : d\mathbf{e}^p} \quad (18)$$

165 where $d\mathbf{e}^p$ is the deviatoric plastic strain rate.

166 To avoid overestimating the inelastic dilatancy, a non-associated plastic flow rule is used in the
167 proposed constitutive model:

$$168 \quad g^p = q - \eta_g p' \quad (19)$$

169 where η_g is the parameter controlling the plastic volume expansion.

170 The plastic strain rate $\dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}^p$ is computed by:

$$171 \quad \dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}^p = \dot{\lambda} \frac{\partial g^p}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}} \quad (20)$$

172 The deviatoric plastic strain rate can be computed by:

$$173 \quad \dot{\gamma}_p = \dot{\lambda} \frac{\partial g^p}{\partial q} \quad (21)$$

174 where $\dot{\lambda}$ is the plastic multiplier which is a non-negative scalar. The plastic consistency
175 condition can be expressed as:

$$176 \quad \dot{f}^p = \frac{\partial f^p}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}} : \dot{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} + \frac{\partial f^p}{\partial \gamma_p} \dot{\gamma}_p + \frac{\partial f^p}{\partial D} \dot{D} = 0 \quad (22)$$

177 The following damage criterion is proposed to describe the evolution of the damage variable:

$$178 \quad f^d(Y_d, D) = 1 - \exp(\alpha Y_d^\beta) - D \quad (23)$$

179 where α and β are parameters which control the evolution rate of the damage variable.

180 The elastic component Y_d^e of the thermodynamic force Y_d is given in Eq. (13). The plastic
181 component Y_d^p is defined as a function of equivalent deviatoric plastic strain:

$$182 \quad Y_d^p = \frac{1}{2\lambda} k_d \gamma_p^2 \quad (24)$$

183 where k_d is a material parameter.

184 The damage consistency condition has the similar form as the plastic one:

$$185 \quad \dot{f}^d = \frac{\partial f^d}{\partial Y_d} \dot{Y}_d + \frac{\partial f^d}{\partial D} \dot{D} = 0 \quad (25)$$

186 **Numerical integration of the constitutive model**

187 To ensure convergence and stability of numerical solution, the proposed model can be integrated
 188 using the implicit Newton-Raphson method. The strain-controlled procedure is adopted in order
 189 to better capture the strain softening behavior and is also the loading mode followed in finite
 190 element and finite difference implementation of constitutive models. Given the state variables
 191 $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_n, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_n^p, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_n^e, D_n, \gamma_p$ and $Y_{d,n}$ at load step n and the total strain increment $\Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1} = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1} - \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_n$ at load
 192 step $n+1$, the objective of the integration is to find correct solutions for the unknown variables:
 193 $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{n+1}, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1}^p, \gamma_{p,n+1}, D_{n+1}$, and $Y_{d,n+1}$ at load step $n+1$. A two-step algorithm consisting of the
 194 elastic trial step and the plastic corrector step is used herein. The numerical integration algorithm
 195 is illustrated in Fig. 3.

196 Assuming that the stress state at step $n+1$ is elastic, the trial stress $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{n+1}^{trial}$ and the trial
 197 thermodynamic force $Y_{d,n+1}^{trial}$ can be computed. There are four possible scenarios: $f^d <$
 198 0 and $f^p < 0$; $f^d > 0$ and $f^p < 0$; $f^d > 0$ and $f^p > 0$; $f^d < 0$ and $f^p > 0$, which are shown in
 199 Fig. 3. Stresses are calculated and updated according to the integration algorithm as illustrated in
 200 Fig. 3. The damage evolution rate \dot{D}_{n+1} is calculated explicitly.

201 The unknown plastic variables for cases (3) and (4) can be computed by solving a set of
 202 nonlinear equations $F(X_{n+1}) = 0$ using the Newton-Raphson scheme. The plastic multiplier
 203 λ_{n+1} is calculated using a single-equation return-mapping algorithm, which can be obtained by
 204 substituting Eqs. (7), (20) and (21) into Eq. (22):

$$205 \quad F(\lambda_{n+1}) = \frac{\partial f^p}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{n+1}} : \left(-\dot{D}_{n+1} \mathbf{C}_0 : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1}^e + \mathbf{C}_{d,n+1} : (\dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_{n+1} - \dot{\lambda}_{n+1} \frac{\partial g^p}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{n+1}}) \right) + \frac{\partial f^p}{\partial \gamma_{p,n+1}} \dot{\lambda}_{n+1} \frac{\partial g^p}{\partial q_{n+1}} +$$

$$206 \quad \frac{\partial f^p}{\partial D_{n+1}} \dot{D}_{n+1} = 0 \quad (26)$$

207 Using the Taylor-series expansion, Eq. (26) is linearized by neglecting higher order terms:

$$208 \quad F(\lambda_{n+1}^{m+1}) = F(\lambda_{n+1}^m) + \frac{\partial F}{\partial \lambda_{n+1}^m} (\lambda_{n+1}^{m+1} - \lambda_{n+1}^m) \quad (27)$$

209 where m is iteration index.

210 By setting $F(\lambda_{n+1}^{m+1}) = 0$, the new λ_{n+1} can be expressed as:

$$211 \quad \lambda_{n+1}^{m+1} = \lambda_{n+1}^m - (J_{n+1}^m)^{-1} F(\lambda_{n+1}^m) \quad (28)$$

212 where $J_{n+1}^m = \frac{\partial F}{\partial \lambda_{n+1}^m}$ is the Jacobian matrix.

Input: $\Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1}, \boldsymbol{\sigma}_n, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_n^p, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_n^e, D_n, \gamma_p$ and Y_{d_n} at step n
Output: $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{n+1}, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1}^p, \gamma_{p,n+1}, D_{n+1}$, and $Y_{d,n+1}$
for $n=1, \dots$, sum

Elastic prediction: Compute elastic trial stress $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{n+1}^{trial}$ and damage force $Y_{d,n+1}^{trial}$

Case 1 $f^p(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{n+1}^{trial}, \gamma_{p,n+1}^{trial}, D_n) < 0$ and $f^d(Y_{d,n+1}^{trial}, D_n) < 0$
None of plastic flow and damage evolution occurs
The elastic trial stress states are updated.

Case 2 $f^d > 0$ and $f^p < 0$ only damage evolution occurs

$$\dot{D}_{n+1} = (1 - \beta_d) \frac{m_d}{\alpha_d} d\varepsilon_{eq,n+1} \exp\left(-\left(\frac{\varepsilon_{eq,n+1}}{\alpha_d}\right)^{m_d}\right) \left(\frac{\varepsilon_{eq,n+1}}{\alpha_d}\right)^{m_d-1}$$

Case 3 $f^d > 0$ and $f^p > 0$ both plastic flow and damage evolution occur

$$\dot{D}_{n+1} = (1 - \beta_d) \frac{m_d}{\alpha_d} d\varepsilon_{eq,n+1} \exp\left(-\left(\frac{\varepsilon_{eq,n+1}}{\alpha_d}\right)^{m_d}\right) \left(\frac{\varepsilon_{eq,n+1}}{\alpha_d}\right)^{m_d-1}$$

The plastic corrector step is executed
 $\dot{\lambda}_{n+1}$ is obtained by solving the following equation using Newton-Raphson scheme:

$$F(\dot{\lambda}_{n+1}) = \frac{\partial f^p}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{n+1}} : \left(-\dot{D}_{n+1} \mathbf{C}_0 : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1}^e + \mathbf{C}_{d,n+1} : (\dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_{n+1} - \dot{\lambda}_{n+1} \frac{\partial g^p}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{n+1}})\right) + \frac{\partial f^p}{\partial \gamma_{p,n+1}} \dot{\lambda}_{n+1} \frac{\partial g^p}{\partial q_{n+1}} + \frac{\partial f^p}{\partial D_{n+1}} \dot{D}_{n+1} = 0$$

Case 4 $f^d < 0$ and $f^p > 0$ only plastic evolution occurs

$$\dot{D}_{n+1} = 0$$

The plastic corrector step is executed, same as above case.
End
Endfor

213

214

Fig. 3 Numerical integration algorithm of the proposed model

215 Anisotropic function

216 Prior to validating the proposed constitutive model, the anisotropic function is first verified against
217 test data. The authors investigated the anisotropic properties of a shale taken from Chongqing City,
218 China. Samples with $\theta = 0^\circ, 30^\circ, 60^\circ$, and 90° (see Fig. 4) were used. Triaxial tests on these
219 samples under confining stresses of $\sigma_3 = 20$ and 30 MPa were carried out and the peak shear
220 stresses were recorded. Fig. 5 shows the relationship between the peak shear stresses vs. the angle
221 θ . It can be seen that the samples with $\theta = 0^\circ$ have highest peak shear stresses and the lowest peak
222 stresses appears at about $\theta = 30^\circ$. Hence, $\theta_{min} = 30^\circ$ for the triaxial tests. The peak shear stresses
223 are normalized with respect to the peak shear stresses at $\theta = 0^\circ$, which are shown in Fig. 6. The
224 proposed anisotropic function $f(\theta)$ is used to predict these anisotropic curves. The parameters k_1 ,
225 d_1, c_1, k_2, d_2, c_2 are determined via the fitting technique and the determined values are $k_1 = 0.44$,
226 $d_1 = -2.14$; $c_1 = 2.6$; $k_2 = 0.68$, $d_2 = -0.8$ and $c_2 = 1.68$. The predicted curve by the function

227 $f^\theta(\theta)$ is also shown in Fig. 6. The proposed anisotropic function can match well with the
228 experimentally obtained anisotropic peak shear stresses.

229

230

Fig. 4. Bedding orientations of the tested shale samples.

231

232

233

Fig. 5 Peak shear stresses vs. θ at confining stresses of $\sigma_3=20$ and 30 MPa.

234

235 Fig. 6 Normalized peak shear stresses vs. θ at confining stresses of $\sigma_3=20$ and 30 MPa.

236

237 Model validation

238 The proposed model is validated against results from a series of triaxial tests on North Sea shales
239 by the Authors and triaxial tests on Opalinus Clay by Favero et al. (2013). The rheology of the
240 North Sea Shale and the Opalinus Clay can be observed as representative of the behavior of quasi-
241 brittle shale (Berre et al. 2996; Gräsle and Plischke, 2011). Parisio et al. (2015) pointed out that
242 Opalinus Clay has a quasi-brittle mechanical behavior. Opalinus Clay and shale all belong to quasi-
243 brittle geomaterials. Crisci et al. (2019) simply refer to it as Opalinus Clay shale. Hence, tests on
244 Opalinus Clay are used to verify the proposed model.

245 Tests on North Sea Shales

246 A total of seven triaxial tests were carried out on the North Sea shale and the observed results were
247 used to validate the proposed model. Two different stress paths as illustrated in Fig. 7 were used
248 for these triaxial tests. For triaxial Tests 1-5, the vertical stress σ_v remains constant while the
249 horizontal stress σ_h increases. For Tests 6-7, σ_v increases while σ_h remains constant.

250 Samples 1-5 were drilled normally to the bedding of shales while samples 6-7 were drilled
251 parallelly to the bedding. Fig. 8 shows the bedding orientations of all samples. Five (Tests 1, 2, 3,
252 6 and 7) of the seven samples were isotropically consolidated while the rest two (Tests 4 and 5)
253 were anisotropically consolidated. Stress states of the seven samples at the beginning of the shear
254 stage are shown in Table 1. The stress-strain curves of these tests were recorded.

255

256

257

Fig. 7 Stress paths for the triaxial tests 1-7.

258

259

Fig. 8 Bedding orientation in samples 1-7.

260 Table 1 Details of the Triaxial Tests.

Test No.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Stress states at beginning of the shear stage (MPa)	$\sigma_v = 12.5$ $\sigma_h = 12.5$	$\sigma_v = 12.5$ $\sigma_h = 12.5$	$\sigma_v = 3.1$ $\sigma_h = 3.1$	$\sigma_v = 4.9$ $\sigma_h = 2.2$	$\sigma_v = 8.3$ $\sigma_h = 5.6$	$\sigma_v = 6$ $\sigma_h = 6$	$\sigma_v = 4.3$ $\sigma_h = 4.3$

261

262 The proposed constitutive model requires 11 parameters excluding the anisotropic related
 263 parameters. Identification of the parameters of the constitutive model is given below. The elastic
 264 properties E and ν can be estimated at 50% of the peak stress of the shear stress-strain curves and
 265 were determined as 1.8 GPa and 0.45, respectively. The triaxial tests show that the shale samples
 266 with $\theta = 0^\circ$ have higher shear strength than samples with $\theta = 90^\circ$, which is consistent with the
 267 findings of Islam and Skalle (2013) on Pierre-1 shale and of Hou (2018) on Chongqing shale.
 268 Hence, in this study, the anisotropic function $f(\theta = 0^\circ)$ is set to 1 when $\theta = 0^\circ$ for Tests 6 and 7.
 269 The plastic parameters h_0 , h_m and q_0 were determined by comparing the yield surfaces to the
 270 experimental data at the onset of plasticity and the peak stresses in the p - q plane (see Fig. 9). The
 271 onset of plasticity is defined as the points at which the stress behavior deviates from the initial
 272 linear portion of the stress-strain diagrams. The determined values for Tests 6 and 7 with $\theta = 0^\circ$
 273 and $k_\theta = 1$ are $h_0 = 3.5$, $h_m = 7.6$, and $q_0 = 10.7$. The yield and failure surfaces for Tests 6 and
 274 7 are represented by solid lines in Fig. 9. The anisotropic function $f(\theta)$ for Tests 1-5 with $\theta = 90^\circ$
 275 is determined to be 0.62. The anisotropic related parameters k_1 , d_1 , c_1 , k_2 , d_2 , c_2 cannot be
 276 determined, as only samples with $\theta = 0^\circ$ and $\theta = 90^\circ$ were tested. Nevertheless, these
 277 anisotropic related parameters will not be used because only two cases $\theta = 0^\circ$ and $\theta = 90^\circ$ are
 278 considered in the following analysis. The determined yield and failure surfaces for Tests 1-5 when
 279 $\theta = 90^\circ$ and $f(\theta = 90^\circ) = 0.62$ are shown by dashed lines in Fig. 9.

280 The calibration of the parameters b , η_g , α and β , k_d is carried out by best fitting the
 281 constitutive model with Test 1. The determined parameters are: $b = 1000$, $\eta_g = 2e - 2$, $\alpha =$
 282 $1e - 3$, $\beta = 6$, and $k_d = 3$. The parameter R of 0.7 is used to control the residual stress in the
 283 numerical modelling.

284

285 Fig. 9 Comparisons between initial yield surface, final yield surface and the corresponding test
 286 data. $\theta = 0^\circ$ for Tests 6 and 7; $\theta = 90^\circ$ for Tests 1-5.

287 The proposed plasticity-damage model is used to reproduce the shear behavior of the tested
288 shale specimens subjected to various stress states. Fig. 10 compares the proposed model and test
289 data in terms of the σ_s vs. ε_v curves and σ_s vs. ε_h curves of shales under isotropic stress states
290 (Tests 1, 2, 3, 6 and 7) and under anisotropic stress states (Tests 4 and 5). σ_s is shear stress and
291 defined as $\sigma_s = \frac{\sigma_v - \sigma_h}{2}$. ε_v is the vertical strain and ε_h refers to the horizontal strain.

292 Overall, it can be seen from the figure that the proposed constitutive model is able to
293 satisfactorily predict the brittle behavior of shales. The proposed model managed to capture the
294 mechanical behaviors of shale samples (Tests 1-5) and samples (Tests 6-7) which are under
295 different stress paths (see Fig. 7 for details). Samples of Tests 6-7 have larger peak shear stresses
296 which are due to the bedding orientation different from Tests 1-5 which are shown in Fig. 8.

297 Good agreement between modelling and experiments are observed for isotropic stress
298 states ($\sigma_v = \sigma_h = 12.5$ MPa for Tests 1 and 2, $\sigma_v = \sigma_h = 3.1$ MPa for Test 3, $\sigma_v = \sigma_h = 6$ MPa
299 for Test 6, $\sigma_v = \sigma_h = 4.3$ MPa for Test 7). A good match is also observed between the model and
300 the experimental results under anisotropical stress states ($\sigma_v = 4.9$ MPa, $\sigma_h = 2.2$ MPa for test 4;
301 $\sigma_v = 8.3$ MPa, $\sigma_h = 5.6$ MPa for test 5). This indicates that the proposed model can capture the
302 effects of initial stress states of samples at the beginning of the loading.

303 Relatively large discrepancy is found between the model and the experimental data for Test
304 5. The sample of Test 5 tend to have a more ductile behavior rather than brittle behavior. The
305 discrepancy is due to the fact that: 1) the proposed model is intended to model the brittle behavior
306 of shales, and 2) only one set of parameters is used in the verification to capture the brittle behavior
307 despite the fact some scatter in experimental results is expected due to natural variability in the
308 samples.

309 In summary, the proposed model has the capability of predicting the brittle behavior of the
310 North Sea shale under various stress states, stress paths and bedding plane orientations. The
311 concept that the damaged materials still possess residual stresses works well in the coupled
312 plasticity-damage models, which can reflect the macroscopic residual stress in stress-strain curves.

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320 Fig. 10 Comparison between model simulation and experimental results in terms of stress-strain
 321 curves. (a) Tests 1 and 2; (b) Test 3; (c) Test 4; (d) Test 5; (e) Test 6; (f) Test 7.

322 *Tests on Opalinus Clay by Favero et al. (2013)*

323 To further validate the capability of the model on predicting the behavior of shales, triaxial tests
 324 on Opalinus Clay by Favero et al. (2013) are used herein. Opalinus Clay is adopted to validate the
 325 model as it can be viewed as representative of the behavior of quasi-brittle shale.

326 Three triaxial tests on Opalinus Clay subjected to confining stresses of 4.5 MPa, 7.7 MPa,
 327 and 13.3 MPa were carried out by Favero et al. (2013). All the samples have the angle $\theta = 0^\circ$
 328 between the loading and the bedding. The anisotropic function $f^\theta(\theta) = 1$ is used herein. Based
 329 on the experimental observations, Favero et al. (2013) concluded that the Young's modulus is
 330 dependent on the confining stresses. The Young's modulus for samples under confining stresses
 331 of 4.5 MPa, 7.7 MPa, and 13.3 MPa are 14 GPa, 15 GPa, and 16 GPa, respectively. The Poisson
 332 ratio ν is 0.35 for all the samples. The plasticity equation values $h_0 = 40$, $h_m = 76$, and $q_0 = 0$
 333 are determined via comparing the yield surfaces to the experimental data at the onset of plasticity
 334 and the peak stresses in the p - q plane. The parameters b , η_g , α and β , k_d are calibrated by best
 335 fitting the constitutive model with Test 2. The determined parameters are: $b = 5000$, $\eta_g = 1.5e -$
 336 2 , $\alpha = 2e - 2$, $\beta = 3.5$, and $k_d = 2.5$. The parameter R of 0.6 is used to control the residual stress
 337 in the numerical modelling.

338 The comparisons between the model simulation and the test data are shown in Fig. 11. The
 339 proposed model results show good agreement with the test data. The model can capture the strain
 340 softening behavior after the peak stress as well as the residual stress of Opalinus Clay. This
 341 indicates that the coupled plasticity-damage models which incorporates the concept that the
 342 damaged materials still retain resistance loads can represent the residual stresses of brittle materials.

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345 Fig. 11 Comparison between model simulation and experimental results in terms of stress-strain
346 curves. (a) Tests 1; (b) Test 2; (c) Test 3.

347 Conclusions

348 A coupled plasticity-damage constitutive model which accounted for the residual strength of the
349 damaged material was developed to predict the mechanical behavior of shales. A non-linear plastic
350 model in which the damage mechanism is coupled by introducing the damage variable was
351 proposed. A non-associated plastic flow rule was adopted in the plastic model. In the damage
352 criterion used in this work, the thermodynamic force is formulated by accounting for the proposed
353 stress state equation based upon the residual strength of the damaged material. Methods to
354 determine the required model parameters and to implement the model in a computer code were
355 presented.

356 The proposed model considered the residual shear stress by considering that the damaged
357 material still possesses some resistance. The model is validated against the triaxial tests on a North
358 Sea shale and on Opalinus Clay. Validation against experimentally obtained data shows that the
359 proposed model can reflect the main features of the quasi-brittle materials in terms of strain-
360 softening after the peak stress, and the residual stress. This indicates that the concept of damaged
361 materials possessing residual stresses can be incorporated in the coupled plasticity-damage models,
362 which can represent the macroscopic residual stress in the stress-strain curves.

363

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- 431

432 **Figure captions**

433 Fig. 1 Schematic diagram of the damage evolution process.

434 Fig. 2 The angle θ between the major principle stress and the plane.

435 Fig. 3 Numerical integration algorithm of the proposed model

436 Fig. 4. Bedding orientation of Hou (2018)'s tested samples

437 Fig. 5 Peak shear stresses vs. θ .

438 Fig. 6 Normalized peak shear stresses vs. θ .

439 Fig. 7 Stress paths for the triaxial tests 1-7.

440 Fig. 8 Bedding orientation in samples 1-7.

441 Fig. 9 Comparisons between initial yield surface, final yield surface and the corresponding test
442 data. $\theta = 0^\circ$ for Tests 6 and 7; $\theta = 90^\circ$ for Tests 1-5.

443 Fig. 10 Comparison between model simulation and experimental results in terms of stress-strain
444 curves. (a) Tests 1 and 2; (b) Test 3; (c) Test 4; (d) Test 5; (e) Test 6; (f) Test 7.

445 Fig. 11 Comparison between model simulation and experimental results in terms of stress-strain
446 curves. (a) Tests 1; (b) Test 2; (c) Test 3.

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448

449 **Table caption**

450 Table 1 Details of the Triaxial Tests.

Test No.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Stress states at beginning of the shear stage (MPa)	$\sigma_v = 12.5$ $\sigma_h = 12.5$	$\sigma_v = 12.5$ $\sigma_h = 12.5$	$\sigma_v = 3.1$ $\sigma_h = 3.1$	$\sigma_v = 4.9$ $\sigma_h = 2.2$	$\sigma_v = 8.3$ $\sigma_h = 5.6$	$\sigma_v = 6$ $\sigma_h = 6$	$\sigma_v = 4.3$ $\sigma_h = 4.3$

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